

Applications of High-Strength-Fiber-Reinforced-Plastic In Building Components of Low-Rise Wood Structures

Dan Tingley P.Eng.
Graduate Research Assistant

Robert J. Leichti
Associate Professor
Department of Forest Products
Oregon State University
Corvallis, Oregon
USA

Abstract

Low rise building structures encompass a wide variety of structure types that are designed for many different service conditions. Modern engineering wood composites are becoming commonplace in the design arena. Now, a working group comprised of academia and industry has developed a high-strength-fiber-reinforced-plastic panel, which is trade marked as FiRP™ Panel and used in conjunction with the glulam etc. (e.g. FiRP™ Glulam), for reinforcing engineered wood products. The first applications are with glulam. However, applications of FiRP™ Panels are envisioned with other engineering wood products such as laminated veneer lumber, I-joists, parallel strand lumber, and others. The emphasis is on the use of reinforcement in glulam because the development work has been focused on that product group. Full-scale glulam beams have been manufactured and tested, and a design method for glulam was developed and verified. Results of testing and design analyses indicate the technology is cost effective due to reductions in lumber volume and grade, transportation costs, chemical treatment costs, and in some cases construction costs. Experiences with the reinforcement technology in the initial heavy timber construction applications are discussed. The authors see several potential design advantages and problems associated with using the reinforcement technology in other products and expect the reinforced products to impact both the material selection and behavior of low-rise structures.

Introduction

New technology is now being implemented in the manufacture of glued laminated wood beams (glulams). This technology involves the use of high-strength fiber reinforced plastics as a reinforcement of the wood and wood composites. It is being marketed in the United States by American Laminators under the trade name SR-1™. This technology is applicable to various types of structural wood composites (see Figure 1). The methods of construction, production of the reinforcement and placement in the wood and wood composite are protected by several patents pending. Relevant design formulation has been developed and methods for predicting the structural member size and configuration as well as reinforcement location and concentration are also patent pending.

The use of the reinforcement in the manufacture of glued laminated wood beams has been commercialized and several structures are in service. This application of the SR-1 technology is being marketed in United States under the trade name FiRP™ Glulam by American Laminators.

Figure 1. Sketches of wood-based composite structural products in which reinforcement with high-strength fiber-reinforced plastic is advantageous.

Test criteria has been accepted by the major building code agency in the United States and subsequent testing to verify developed formulas is underway. Laminated beam manufacturers have purchased licenses and several within the United States, Europe and Japan have now begun negotiations to obtain licenses to use the technology for the production of glued laminated wood beams.

The testing necessary for code compliance completion involves over 600 full scale reinforced glulams to verify the developed formulation for allowable strength design work. Testing to date has included a variety of wood species and high strength fiber types in the FiRP™ Panel as well as placement positions and concentrations of reinforcement within the beam [24, 25, 26, 27]. Component testing has also been completed to verify the individual FiRP™ Panel reinforcement properties as well as the composite beam strength characteristics.

In addition to the glued laminated beam reinforcement work, testing of reinforcement of flange material for use in "I" beams has been completed. Testing has indicated a substantial benefit in many areas. The predominant benefit is in the use of low grade species to replace the more costly high grade tension stock that is necessary in the production of "I" beams.

The economical advantage when reinforcement is used in the manufacture of glulams is so substantial (net 25-30%) that reinforced glulams are now being considered for other uses such as axial compression members (columns) and tension members lower chords of glulam trusses. Structural members used in combined bending and axial loading situations are also being considered. This type of investigation using similar methods has been conducted by others [13] with unreinforced wood members. In addition to the use of reinforcement in the production of glued laminated wood beams reinforcement in the production of other wood and wood composites used in structural situations has potential.

These alternate uses for reinforced glulams require additional design guidelines for proper implementation. Design criteria can be developed with traditional methods for glulam design combined with new formulations for reinforced beam design currently being verified by physical testing. There are potential problems with the indiscriminate use of reinforcement in all situations. This paper discusses the advantages of reinforcement and outlines areas that need to be evaluated when investigating its use in the manufacture of reinforced wood and wood composites.

Background

Reinforcement of wood and wood composites has been attempted in many ways including the use of pretensioned piano wires in the high stress zones [15], the use of steel bars similar to those used in reinforced concrete as a reinforcing [4], tapered splines to reinforce shear capacity [10] and flitch plate designs and the traditional external steel tension rod systems. All have been used to reinforce the wood system and provide for increased load capacity. These concepts have not gained wide commercial acceptance since production requirements were unacceptable and the economic benefits minimal [3, 28, 29]. Most innovations involved the use of different kinds of glues that were not acceptable to most wood manufacturers [12, 18, 19]. The mechanical advantages were found to be minimal with existing FiRP™ Panel manufacturing techniques [8].

The new system being implemented under the trade name FiRP™ Glulams has alleviated many of these problems for the manufacturers, making the use of FiRP™ Glulams economical [7, 16, 21, 22]. The FiRP™ Panel is produced in much the same way as other unidirectional high-strength fiber reinforced plastics with two important exceptions: the fibers are all pretensioned and they are all aligned parallel to the long axis of the FiRP™ Panel. The degree alignment affects the quality of the FiRP™ Panel. The matrix or plastic used to carry the fibers in an aligned pretensioned condition can be varied to suit the design specifications. A wide range of matrix plastics are used, including thermoset types from polyester to epoxy, thermoplastic types like Nylon 66 or PET as well as fibers from fiberglass to carbon. The FiRP™ Panel is prepared with a proprietary method that allows it to adhere to the wood and other FiRP™ Panels using conventional resorcinol glues and current manufacturing practices. If desired, the FiRP™ Panel can be passed through the glue spreader just as the wood laminates are. The same layup pressures, open times, and close times [27] are necessary.

There are limitless structural applications for wood and wood composites reinforced with FiRP™ Panels. The most important are the long span support systems where dead weight of the support system is critical in the design. Reinforcement reduces the net cross section of the structural member for a given load [11, 17, 23]. Thus, wood domes, large roof systems, bridges [26] and main support beams are the first structural applications that have been considered. To date six structures have been constructed including long span beams for large buildings and bridges. Currently nearly 40 million dollars (US) of structures are in the design stages using FiRP™ Glulam technology. Included in this work is the largest free standing structure to be built in the world, a 720 foot (220 m.) clear span, rectangular dome to be built in Japan.

Another important application of this new FiRP™ Glulam technology is the reinforcement of continuous tension and compression chords in trusses and other axially loaded members. Design methodology for unreinforced glulams is readily available (NDS 1991) and similarly such groups as Dupont [5], Hercules [9] and Permanez [17] have published design data for FiRP™ Panels such as aramid-reinforced plastic (ARP), carbon reinforced plastic (CRP) and fiberglass reinforced plastic (FRP) respectively. Many researchers have investigated the characteristics of FiRP™ Panel-wood composites [2, 18, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29] but none have developed exact manufacturing and design criteria for structural members. The use of high strength fiber reinforced plastics as reinforcement for various wood and wood composites needs a substantial amount of research and investigation before wholesale usage can be implemented.

Typical Approach To The Problem

The cost of full scale research in the area of reinforcement, marginal economical assessments and suitable, economically priced suitable supplies of high grade wood fiber have prevented any effective development of the reinforcement concept in the wood and wood composite (WWC) industry. The literature in public domain consists mostly of mathematical modeling of the use of reinforcement. One of the most popular methods of completing such analyses is the use of finite element (FE) models. A FE model assists in the examination of the probable stress distribution in the reinforced glulams subjected to loads. The response of the model is determined by the assignment of properties to the various components of the reinforced wood model. Samuel [20] and Balinski [1] adequately describe the use of computers for mathematical modeling. Davalos [8]

found the use of FE modeling to be satisfactory for stress distribution analysis in fiberglass reinforced plastic (FRP) reinforcement of glulams.

Problems To Be Overcome When Modeling

The accuracy of the predicted stress distribution within the wood and FiRP™ Panel is an important feature of the FE analysis. The accuracy of the predicted strain distribution within the wood and FiRP™ Panel is also important. The development of the individual component properties seems to be a matter of properly researching the physical properties of the components. However, the FiRP™ Panel suitable for gluing to the wood must have surface characteristics that allow it to be adhered to the wood using conventional adhesives such as phenol resorcinol glues. When the FiRP™ Panel is manufactured in this way its properties change dramatically when compared to the properties of the typical high strength fiber reinforced plastic panel specified by many of the plastics composites manufacturers.

Another critical area of consideration in conducting a FE analysis is the assumption of complete stress translation versus partial stress translation across gluelines. With regard to the wood to wood interfaces this concern is relatively small. However, the integrity of the gluelines between the two materials (wood and reinforcement) and proper understanding of this transition zone are critical to the modeling of the overall stress distribution. Typically small scale laboratory experiments involving the testing of wood in solid form or laminated form reinforced with a high strength fiber reinforced plastic have used epoxy type glues to adhere the two materials together. This type of adhesive is not user friendly and is too expensive to be suitable in the manufacturing environment. These type of small scale experiments must be viewed with an understanding that when the typical adhesives are used in the production of full scale test specimens the stress distributions across gluelines at the wood FiRP™ Panel interface may change. A substantial amount of strain data for tensile and compressive forces acting on FiRP™-wood composites has been collected [23]. This data, combined with component testing in tension and compression of FiRP™ Panel and wood, has provided a valuable source of information for the analytical modeling and FE analysis.

The results have shown that several factors are critical if FE models are to accurately predict the response of the full scale reinforced WWC. First, the bond line between the FiRP™ Glulam and the wood should not exceed .004" (.1 mm). Second, the shear strength of the glueline must be substantial enough to develop 95% shear failures (AITC T107 standard shear block tests) in the shoulder of the glueline in both the wood and FiRP™ Panel. Third, the values of ultimate shear strength in the FiRP™ Panel must exceed 1200 psi. (8.28 MPa). These are important considerations in the construction of economical reinforced WWC's. Fourth, the FiRP™ Panel must be produced in such a way as to allow the wood to shrink and expand with moisture changes. Theoretically, this dimensional change could reach magnitudes in the range of 7%.

Material Comparisons

Wood in its basic form has the highest specific tensile strength of all materials. In its solid sawn form, it contains defects such as slope of grain and knots that substantially reduce its overall tensile strength. Glulams are manufactured with carefully selected laminates of wood. These laminates have been visually and structurally graded [26] to provide for higher strength structural members. However, they are still limited by the basic defects, either natural, such as knots, or manufactured, such as fingerjoints.

High-strength fibers have a homogeneous form and can be manufactured in more consistent forms. In particular, they can be manufactured in continuous lengths. In addition, they have a very high tensile and compressive strength and modulus. For example, ARP has a tensile strength of 200,000 psi. (1380 MPa). CRP has a tensile or compressive modulus of 18.5×10^6 (6) psi. (127,500 MPa). This compares with values of 15,000 psi. (100 MPa) and 1.8×10^6 (6) psi. (12,400 MPa) for tensile strength and modulus of Douglas-fir at 12% moisture content [26]

respectively. The addition of FiRP™ Panels to glulams for axially loaded members allows much higher axial stresses to be transmitted through the composite beam. In particular, if the FiRP™ Panel is interconnected between adjoining beams, substantially higher stresses can be conducted through the member.

Product Applications--Potential and Problems

There are many WWC product applications for FiRP™ Panels as outlined in the introduction. Each product application has particular requirements for the proper use of the reinforcement panel.

Glued Laminated Beam

During the manufacture of FiRP™ Glulams several positive characteristics of the FiRP™ Panel reinforcement have become evident. The long term load resistance of the reinforcement, particularly in high moisture environments, has improved the creep response of FiRP™ Glulams substantially over unreinforced glulams. Recent research completed by Tingley [23] has shown that the deflection that occurs after initial loading to stress levels (extreme fiber in tension under bending) in the range of 4300 psi (29.65 MPa) in wood fiber adjacent to the reinforcement is 94% less than unreinforced wood at stress levels with similar methods of loading of 2000 psi. (13.80 MPa). The load deflection curves from full scale testing of beams in bending in a wet condition (moisture content > 20%) show no noticeable reduction in bending strength or Modulus of Elasticity in bending (MOEb).

The effect on Modulus of Rupture in bending (MORb) of localized defects in the FiRP™ Glulam cross section is substantially reduced such that reinforced glulams can be manufactured with low grade wood such as L-3 Douglas-fir (AITC 117-93) throughout the reinforced beam, butt joints not glued instead of fingerjoints glued, slope of grain of 1:4, juvenile wood and stacked butt joints and replace high grade premium Douglas-fir unreinforced glulams. This also reduces the liability of the manufacturer. Poor quality adhesion in the fingerjoints no longer affects the MORb appreciably in reinforced glulams whereas it can be a principal cause of premature failure in unreinforced glulams. Concentrated loads can lead to localized stress distribution problems in the lower portion of unreinforced beams. No such problems exist with the reinforced glulams.

Other Wood and Wood Composites

The use of FiRP™ Panels in the production of various WWC's is now being investigated. The initial indications suggest that there are substantial economic benefits when FiRP™ Panels are used to reinforce WWC's. However, there are many areas of potential problems. The most important of the potential problem areas is the development of proper shear performance values between the wood and the reinforcement and, in cases of multiple layers of reinforcement, between the layers of reinforcement. This concern has not been readily understood since the proper development of shear performance has numerous considerations.

The major consideration is the moisture stability of the wood to that of reinforcement (WD-R) and reinforcement to reinforcement (R-R). The changes in moisture contents (MC) of the wood during the lifetime of the WWC will produce dimensional changes that could theoretically create dimensional changes in the 5-7% range (Douglas-fir). The FRP does not undergo dimensional change with fluctuating moisture content. Thus the changes in MC over the lifetime of a FiRP™ Glulam could conceivably lead to high levels of shear stress in the WD-R gluelines due to dimensional change. Depending upon the species and the FRP surface shear capacity this can lead to failure of the glueline, in service, of the reinforced WWC due to dimensional changes introduced during moisture content fluctuations. Generally, cyclic delamination tests such as AITC T110 are important qualifications of any reinforced WWC. These tests isolate the ability of the glueline to withstand all dimensional change stresses that are induced during moisture content fluctuations. FiRP™ Glulams undergo five cycles of AITC T110 instead of the conventional one cycle to insure that the WD-R gluelines will stand the test of time in service under various MC conditions.

Small test specimens of wood and FRP's used for shear strength tests generally exclude the wet service strength characteristics of the FRP. Most WWC's are produced at moisture contents (MC) in the 12-14 % range. This is well above the saturation points of most of the common fiber reinforced plastics (FRP). Many fibers used in the production of FRP's undergo a substantial loss of strength in wet conditions ($\leq 9\%$ for fiberglass reinforced plastic). The long term load resistance of FRP's varies substantially. Fiberglass reinforced plastic for example, losses approximately half of its long term load resistance in a saturated condition, $\geq 9\%$ MC, which is less than what the WWC is manufactured at. In such cases the long term load resistance of fiberglass reinforced plastic drops from 46% of ultimate tensile strength (UTS) to 26% of UTS in saturated condition. When aramids are used there is no appreciable drop in long term load resistance between dry and wet conditions. In both situations aramid reinforced plastics maintain 92% of UTS in tension in either dry or wet environments.

The effects on the shear strengths of the FRP of the moisture content need to be considered. Thus when considering the shear performance of the WD-R and R-R interface it is important to consider the effects of dimensional change and wet shear performance. One additional point is geometric considerations. FRP's generally have higher MOEt (tension), MOEb, MOEc (compression), shear modulus (G) and Poisson ratios in various directions. Since the FRP's used as reinforcements are generally unidirectional and contain a majority of the fiber in a longitudinal orientation, they have dramatically different flexure characteristics. These flexure characteristics lead to what is termed geometric considerations (GC). The GC considerations can cause delamination problems in the WD-R interface in situations involving cyclic loading of the WWC and in load ranges approximating ultimate load. This phenomena is exaggerated in high MC situations. Generally speaking the greater the deflection the greater the potential of delamination due to these anomalies.

When reinforcement is used in the flange of I beams, deflection can be a particular problem. In such situations the flange usually contains low grade wood with a FRP and the amount of reinforcement is generally very small. The percentage of FRP in the flange may be similar to the percentage by cross section of FRP that is used in the manufacture of reinforced glulams but the total amount of wood and the total amount of FRP used in the system is much less. In such situations the geometric considerations are important. Allowable deflection may lead to radius of curvature in the reinforcement compared to the thickness of reinforcement well over the acceptable ranges for the WD-R interface. If conventional mechanical adhesion techniques with resorcinol type glue systems which depend upon porous plastic matrices are employed in the WD-R interface then delamination within deflection ranges of $L/180$ to $L/240$ may occur. This phenomena may occur even when the cyclic delamination tests and shear strengths meet acceptable minimums.

When the reinforcement is used with I beams where the web material passes through the reinforcement such as with steel web-wood flange I beams the shear strength of the reinforcement in the longitudinal-thickness plane needs to be carefully reviewed. This strength is dependent upon the matrix in 100% longitudinally aligned fiber reinforced plastic. The fiber concentration will also directly affect this strength. Ultimate stress levels of 600 psi (4.14 MPa) for polyester to 4600 psi. (31.72 MPa) epoxy type matrices at 60% fiber volume are conventional ranges. Thus the design shear strength for web/flange interface considerations are important and need proper testing and analysis before manufacture and marketing of products for service. This same shear performance is also a consideration with bolts that pass through the reinforcement.

When reinforcement is used with Laminated Veneer Lumber (LVL) it generally serves to reduce the amount of high grade veneers that are required. Since LVL is used in situations where shear is often the governing criteria it is important to note that the fibers in the FRP need to be split between parallel to axis and off axis orientation to match the design criteria. Thus the 100% aligned fiber reinforced plastic used in the reinforcement of a glued laminated beam where deflection and moment are governing in design would not be suitable for the reinforcement of a LVL product where shear was the governing design criteria.

When reinforcement is placed adjacent to large knots ($\geq 7/8$ in. (22.23 mm.)) testing conducted for the commercialization of FiRP™ Glulams isolates that a 15% increase in MORb can be obtained by limiting such knots to the outside 2/3 of the beam (lengthwise for beams in bending). The large knots tended to cause stress concentrations that lead to premature failure when combined with similar knots in the wood laminations adjacent to the reinforcement in the central portions of

beams in bending in the tension zone. FRP™ Panels used to reinforce WWC's in compression zones the knots tended to improve the load capacity of the WWC. Fire considerations for reinforced WWC's also require discussion. If the reinforcement is concealed inside the WWC then the char rate of the wood in larger structural members ($\geq 4''$ minimum dimension) generally mean that the reinforced member will have a fire rating at least equal to the unreinforced member. In situations where the reinforcement is concealed but the member is smaller in dimension and in situations where the reinforcement is placed on the outside of the WWC the fire resistance of the reinforced WWC needs to be considered.

Summary

If the WWC industry world wide is to become successful in fully implementing this needed technology and becoming more competitive with steel and concrete it must recognize and appreciate the differences between wood and plastic and make the necessary allowances in the full scale product.

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